

Sugarcane Marketing and Production in Tamilnadu - A Case Study

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Abstract

The world population is increasing day by day and would demand more food besides the natural resources like land and water. Keeping in view the need of 7 billion world population, agriculture will need more land and water to produce enough food grains. Availability of natural resources is depleting at faster rate. Thus, to fulfill the needs of future population would be more challenging task for farming communities. Sugarcane is one of the multi-product main cash crop of India, and its use for sugar and renewable energy (production of ethanol), the task has become more challenging than ever before to cope-up the demand of adequate sugarcane production in spite of the shrinking available natural resources.

This paper is main focus of the study Cost of production, Gross and Net Returns of Sugarcane, Sugarcane - Break-up of Cost of Cultivation, Growth rates of area under sugarcane cultivation-state wise total, Fertilizer recommendations in sugarcane and Fertilizer recommendations for sugarcane in major sugarcane growing states of India, Beneficiaries of small and large farmers' in Insurance Scheme.

Keywords: Production, Net Returns, Break-up, recommendations, Beneficiaries.

Introduction

Indian Sugar Mills Association (ISMA) has lowered India's 2018-19 sugar production estimate by 2.5% to 307 lakh tonnes from first advance estimate of 315 lakh tonnes issued in October 2018. ISMA has procured the satellite images of cane area already harvested and remaining unharnessed area in the fields, across the country during mid-season i.e. in the second week of January 2019. “On the basis of these images of harvested and balance area, trend of yields and sugar recoveries. Brazil, traditionally the world's top sugar producer, is poised to cede the crown to India for the first time in 16 years.

Production in the Asian country this season may rise 5.2 per cent to a record 35.9 million metric tonnes on increasing acreage and improving yields, the US Department of Agriculture's Foreign Agricultural Service said on Tuesday in a report. Brazil's output may tumble 21 per cent to 30.6 million tonnes because of adverse weather and a shift to produce more cane base . Global production is forecast to fall 4.5 per cent to 185.9 million tonnes, trailing the May estimate of 188.3 million, after the outlooks for Brazil, Thailand and the European Union were revised lower.

Sugarcane market in Tamil Nadu

Sugar mills in Tamil Nadu are facing a double whammy as one more year of sugarcane deficit looms in 2018-19 (October-September) season. But in the backdrop of domestic sugar glut, the Centre's relief measures designed to tackle the oversupply only add to the woes of the sugar companies. Sugar mills in the State are working at 25-30 per cent capacity utilisation, against an installed capacity of about 30 lakh tonnes (lt) due to sustained dry spell in recent years. Last season, the total sugar output was about 10 lakh tonnes. Also, for the third year in a row, sugar recovery has dropped below 9 per cent, while top producers such as Uttar Pradesh and Maharashtra get around 11 per cent. So, on every tonne of sugarcane, mills in the State make much less sugar.

No transparency in quota

According to industry sources, there is no transparency in the monthly release mechanism. Despite repeated representations by the South Indian Sugar Mills Association – Tamil Nadu, the Centre has not clarified the formula on which the quota is set, they say. The State's monthly sugar consumption is about 1.25 lakh tonnes (lt), about 15 lt, annually. But since June, when the system was established, monthly releases ranged between 18,696 tonnes and 54,095 tonnes. This means sugar from other States is sold here and local mills are displaced from the market.

Similarly, the export quota has also proved adverse to Tamil Nadu. The export volume per mill is set based on the production of the last three years. In Tamil Nadu, sugar production has been dropping consistently. If the previous year's production is high then they end up exporting more. So in other States mills are expected to export about 14 per cent of production, Tamil Nadu mills will have to export about 21 per cent. Ideally, the mills should be exempted from exports or a fixed proportion of about 10 per cent should be set, according to SISMA representatives.

Sugar Marketing Policy

According to industry sources, the sugar industry will continue to be subject to production controls by state governments, including sugar industry licensing, cane area reservation, minimum distance criteria, adoption of the cane price formula, specified cane procurement areas for sugar mills, and cane pricing. On a side note, the sugar procurement for public distribution system (PDS) operation is being made from the open market by the state/Union Territories, and the Government is providing a fixed subsidy at INR 18.50 per kg for restricted coverage only to the Antyodaya Anna Yojana (AAY) families who will be provided 1 kg of sugar per family per month.

Ethanol Program

The ethanol blended program (EBP) seeks to achieve blending of ethanol with gasoline with a goal to reduce pollution, encourage value addition along the value chain, and improve cash flows, particularly with the goal to clear cane price arrears of farmers. Per the latest Post estimate, India's ethanol production in MY 2017/18 is likely 2.6 billion liters (from molasses), 50 percent above last year and the highest in the last decade. The previous record production was 2.4 billion liters in MY 2006/07.

Assuming that there is a price incentive for selling ethanol, states with surplus will be encouraged to sell more ethanol for blending with gasoline. Likewise, potable consumption is also expected to rise in tandem, while imported ethanol (if competitive) will fill demand for industrial use. Theoretically, the ethanol available is sufficient to meet the 7 percent blend target, but viably will meet a 3.4 percent market penetration in MY 2017/18.

Description of the study area

Tamil Nadu is one of the most well known and important states in India, situated in the Southern part of the country. It lies in the coordinate of 200N and 770E. Tamil Nadu is surrounded by lands on its north (Karnataka and Andhra Pradesh) and west (Kerala), as well as by water bodies of Indian Ocean and Bay of Bengal on its south and east respectively. To its extreme north, there is Pulicat Lake and the southern tip is formed by Kanyakumari or Cape Comorin. The Mudumulai Wildlife Sanctuary forms the western limit and the Point Calimere forms the eastern limit of Tamil Nadu. The mountain ranges of the Eastern Ghats and Western Ghats run along the boundaries of the state and meet at the Nilgiri Hills.

Nature and source of Data

The secondary data was collected for analysis from A Monthly Magazine Indian Sugar The present study was conducted in the state of Tamil Nadu. In Tamil Nadu, all the thirty two districts were selected for making a detailed study

The study period

In accordance with the objective delineated, the time-series data pertaining to the production of total sugarcane production (000 tones) and yield (t/ha) for over a long span of 25 years time, i.e.1991 to 2015 had been brought under the purview of the present analysis..

Growth rate study on time series production factors on sugarcane.

A number of studies were undertaken to understand the growth pattern of production and productivity under sugarcane crop in Tamil Nadu and India.

The statistics, viz., Mean, Standard error, Coefficient of variation (CV) and percentage figures were computed in respect of the above factors for the Tamil Nadu and also for India as a whole. The coefficient of variation criterion indicated the consistency of factors over years. In order to study the growth rate, the well-known growth model was fitted with respect to each factor.

The model is

where, $X_{it} = \alpha \beta^t \epsilon_{it}$ $i = 1, 2, \dots, 8; t = 1, 2, \dots, 25$
 $\log X_{it} = \log \alpha + t \log \beta$

- X_{it} = the response of the i th factor in the t th year,
- α, β = unknown parameters to be estimated in the model,
- t = time element which takes the value 1,2,3,... n
- ϵ_{it} = multiplicative error
- $\epsilon_s \sim \text{IID } N(0, \sigma^2)$

The above growth model was linearised by using logarithmic transformation and the unknown parameters were estimated by the ordinary least squares (OLS) method. From the fitted model compound growth rate percentage was computed as

$$\text{CGR \%} = (\text{Antilog } b - 1) \times 100$$

Where,

b = Estimated value of β .

Descriptive and growth rate study on time series production factors on sugarcane

Table 1.1 Fitted the growth models and Compound growth rates of

factors of Sugarcane during 1991 to 2015

Factors	Fitted growth models		CGR (%)	
	India	T.N.	India	T.N.
X1	$X1 = 3546.06 \times 1.02t$	$X1 = 257.44 \times 1.01t$	1.51	0.83
Y=X2	$X2 = 37679.10 \times 1.02t$	$X2 = 27555.80 \times 1.00t$	1.55	0.47
X3	$X3 = 67.04 \times 1.00t$	$X3 = 107.46 \times 0.996t$	0.03	-0.41
X4	$X4 = 111467.43 \times 1.03t$	$X4 = 13759.1.01t$	3.38	1.45
X5	$X5 = 11057.04 \times 1.04t$	$X5 = 1249.61 \times 1.02t$	3.54	1.51
X6	$X6 = 9.93 \times 1.00t$	$X6 = 9.09 \times 1.00t$	0.15	0.06
X7	$X7 = 372.04 \times 1.01t$	$X7 = 30.53 \times 1.01t$	1.44	1.34
X8	$X8 = 23.62 \times 1.08t$	$X8 = 23.62 \times 1.08t$	8.50	8.50

Table inference

Table -1.1 reveals the growth dynamics of the sugarcane production factors for India and Tamil Nadu during the period 1991 to 2015. From the table, it is seen that the maximum compound growth rate had been obtained at the minimum statutory price of sugarcane i.e. 8.50% in India as well as in Tamil Nadu. In both the cases, the minimum growth rate is observed in sugarcane yield i.e. 0.03% in India and -0.41 % in Tamil Nadu.

In case of India as a whole, the significant increase has been occurred in cane area (1.51%), production (1.51%), cane crushed (3.38%), sugar production (3.54%) and the decline in growth rate had occurred in yield i.e. 0.03% and average recovery of sugar percent i.e. 0.15%. Though the compound growth rates for Tamil Nadu state record significant increase (per year) with respect to the factors cane crushed (1.45%), sugar production (1.51%) and number of factories in operation (1.34) yet surprisingly, the negative growth rates for the factor sugarcane productivity (-0.41) has occurred. This observation, however, is also in nice consonance with the earlier observations. More efforts should be geared to bring these areas at par with national level. The growth rate scenarios for most of the factors with respect to India are quite satisfactory as, in these areas, positive significant growth rates loudly substantiate the theme of national advancement.

Average and coefficient of variation with respect to sugarcane production factors

Table 1.2 Contributions to India from Tamil Nadu During 1991 to 2015

Factors	Fitted growth models		CGR (%)		Percentage of TN to India
	India	T.N.	India	T.N.	
X1	4347.2	13.48	290.68	16.36	6.69
Y=X2	293247.08	14.82	29860.56	19.65	10.18
X3	67.38	4.32	102.06	6.22	151.45
X4	179660.92	30.66	17243.40	28.26	9.60
X5	18236.96	31.70	1578.60	28.26	8.66
X6	10.13	2.34	9.17	4.56	90.56
X7	451.0	11.57	36.48	11.03	8.09
X8	82.07	66.32	82.07	66.32	100

Table inference

Table -1.2 shows the averages, coefficient of variations with respect to sugarcane factors and their percentage contributions to India from Tamil Nadu. Average values of factors corresponding to Tamil Nadu and India as a whole are not comparable as percentage figures related to Tamil Nadu in comparison to those of all India show significant contribution on the part of this state to the national scene for most of the factors which can be observed from this table. The table indicated that Tamil Nadu contributes 6.69% in area, 10.18% in production, 9.60% in cane crushed, 8.66% in sugar production, 8.09% in a number of factories in operation to India. The cane yield in Tamil Nadu is 151.45% higher than the nation's productivity and the sugar recovery is 90.52% higher.

Moreover, the values of the coefficients of variation reveal the existence of greater inconsistency (fluctuation) in the data. From the table, it is noted that the maximum coefficient of variation is observed in Minimum support price in India as well as in Tamil Nadu i.e. 66.325. The minimum coefficient of variation is observed in an average recovery of sugar percent in India (2.34%) and Tamil Nadu (4.56%). Hence, we conclude that the most stable factor is an average recovery of sugar percent and maximum fluctuation is observed in Minimum support price.

Conclusion

The study diagnoses the influential factors affecting the sugarcane production in Tamil Nadu and in India as a whole by adopting the technique of correlation and path analysis. It is found that though the scenario of influential factors on total sugarcane and sugar production is explicitly clear in the context of India yet the same is not so in the case of Tamil Nadu state.

The power model is found to be best fitted for Tamil Nadu cane production and productivity. But it is found that compound model is a well-fitted model for sugarcane production in India. Again power model is best fitted for Indian cane yield. The maximum fluctuation has been observed in Minimum Support Price followed by Sugar production and cane crushed. The average recovery of sugar percent has been found the most stable factor in India as well as in Tamil Nadu. The most direct influential factor for sugarcane production is area and indirect influential is sugar production.

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